

8T – Variational Fermion Distributions & Dark matter

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Abstract:

By analyzing the new framework of variational manifolds in the second representation, i.e. universe packets, it is possible to expand the idea of "dark matter" by stating that the matter distributions of two interacting manifolds does not have to be exact, the exactness condition is of the total curvature associated with the cluster. The result of such a condition is a gravitational effect around areas of extremum curvature not perfectly placed on them. In other words, "dark matter" is a variational fermionic distribution from a distinct manifold, which is close to our own manifold and as a result, those two distributions create an additional mass trace, or an additional pressure.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the matric tensor M, given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other matric tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.1). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant. Flatness is an immediate result of this framework as given by the illustration below.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^K \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_m} \frac{\partial s_m}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=1}^K \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2.A)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matric tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron by putting it in the fine structure constant formula:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

We have described the arbitrary variations of the manifold by the term on the main equation:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.46)$$

We partitioned and discretized the arbitrary variation term and derived the existence of Fermion. In particular, we have shown that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \quad (1.47)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.48)$$

In addition, with bosons, described by the term (1.49) as they were proven discrete amount of prime curvature on the matric tensor:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.49)$$

We have presented the spin classification in the 8T thesis, page seventeen, while using the prime critical line:

Spin 0: $2N_0$ variations

Spin $\frac{1}{2}$: $2N_0 + 3$ variations

Spin 1: $2N_0 + 3 + N_V$ variations

Spin $N = 2N_0 + 3 + N_{V1} + N_{V2} \dots$ variations

Let us analyze the idea of dark matter. Author submitted two options in the 8T thesis. The first in pages (25-28) which has to do with the Quark masses series. Such a series was derived as a result of trying to eliminate the question of three families, and by simple rescale of the third and the first a pattern was found. The rate of convergence to zero however is rather fast and thus already in the fifth family we reach total mass aspiring zero. The rate of convergence to zero could indicate that it is not sufficient to be the sole cause of dark matter. The second explanation in thesis pages (123-124), used to universe packet representation, i.e. a gravitational effect from a distinct manifold. In this paper, author is going to expand on the second explanation, which is variational matter distributions of distinct manifold of the same class. Let us use the universe packet pairs, with opposite curvature orientations, which flatten each other. Let the arbitrary variations distributions be identical in amount but different across each area of extremum curvature such as galaxy.

As an example one took a set of two distinct Lorentz manifolds, which invoked stationary:

$$\wp = [s_1, s_2]$$

$$s_n = (M, g)$$

To each associate a finite number of arbitrary variations which vanish into matter, isomorphic to each other. This cluster of arbitrary variations vanish into a galaxy.

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i \in s_1$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^K \delta g_i \in s_2$$

$$K \equiv M$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^K \delta g_i \sim \sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i \quad (1.62)$$

This cluster has the same amount of matter. The key point is that despite the clusters are isomorphic the Fermionic distributions could be different. If one manifold has a star like earth at the matrix, that fact does not mean that the complimentary manifold has a star at the exact place, or any star at all. The exactness condition using that framework does not include exact matter distributions but rather isomorphic number of arbitrary variations in the total cluster. Define one fermion distribution at an interval:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i \rightarrow \mathcal{R}^{s_1} \in [0,1]$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^K \delta g_i \rightarrow \mathcal{R}^{s_2} \in [0,1]$$

$$\mathcal{R}^{s_1} \neq \mathcal{R}^{s_2}$$

If one considers that variational distributions are not identical while the clusters of total variations are isomorphic, the result is invisible matter traces within each manifold. It is more reasonable to assume the distributions are different rather to assume they are identical at the a star of a scale. Is it possible to assume that two equal amounts of gas projectile at the same space would diffuse the exact same molecule distributions? We can only take the average in such cases and state that the total distributions must be identical overtime, i.e. spread over the limits of the space. Those invisible matter distributions are the role of dark energy according to this idea. Other universes is not a question anymore, 8T correlate the major features of our own universe to their existence. Dark energy is given by universe packet, as a result flatness as well. Those are proven, agreed upon measurable facts, i.e. the flatness and dark energy, which can not be solved assuming there exist only one universe. It could be even possible to estimate the distance between each two universe assuming we know the added gravitational effect added by dark matter.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

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